

Supporting appendices for: “The hunt for research data: development of an open-source workflow for tracking institutionally affiliated research data publications”

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Appendix A. Case studies on metadata discrepancies and plasticity

As mentioned in the main text, the workflow's development was shaped by discovery of numerous metadata deficiencies and discrepancies at the repository level. Understanding the full history is not essential for re-using the workflow, but case studies involving four repositories (Dryad, Figshare, Mendeley Data, Texas Data Repository) are described here to provide context for anyone who may be interested in specific examples that informed this workflow.

Texas Data Repository

The first case study pertains to historic suboptimal formatting of affiliation metadata in the Texas Data Repository (TDR), UT Austin's institutional data repository; at the onset of this project, TDR deposits were not detected via ROR- or single-permutation-string DataCite queries. Cross-validation revealed that this was because affiliations for TDR datasets were being crosswalked to DataCite as a string enclosed in parentheses: '(University of Texas at Austin).' This is an unexpected permutation of the institutional name (this formatting occurs in a few other repositories) and one that was not intentional per communications with TDR staff.

This formatting explains, in part, the initial inability to discover TDR datasets through the DataCite API (the absence of a leading "The" being the other explainer), and because of the relative volume of TDR deposits, '(University of Texas at Austin)' became the most commonly identified permutation across all affiliated datasets once the workflow was modified to retrieve them (see archived conference presentations by Shensky and Gee 2024; Gee 2025c). This crosswalk issue was raised with the TDR development team and resolved, with DataCite records for all existing datasets subsequently batch-updated prior to the most recent presentation in April 2025 (Gee and Shensky 2025). TDR deposits are now listed with 'University of Texas at Austin' (which

is still not the official permutation), and ‘(University of Texas at Austin)’ is now the 7th most frequently recovered permutation (Fig. 2). As discussed in the main text, it is hoped that the recently implemented functionality to add ROR identifiers in TDR will further improve the metadata quality.

Dryad

The second case study pertains to unexpected and erroneous changes to data metadata in Dryad. During this project, comparisons were made between repositories with respect to their annual publication volume of UT Austin-affiliated datasets through the use of the *publicationYear* field in DataCite. Early in development, Dryad exhibited an essentially flat pattern over the past decade, oscillating between a narrow range of about 35 to 45 annual datasets with at least one UT Austin researcher listed (Shensky and Gee 2024; Fig. 10). Prior to the most recent presentation in April 2025 (Gee and Shensky 2025), the workflow returned a peculiar pattern for Dryad, with a sharp drop-off to single-digit volume in 2024, but a 2025 volume that was already at the level of previous years (Fig. A1), despite being only a third of the way into the calendar year. This peculiar pattern was not detected for any other high-use repositories that were identified in the workflow.

Figure A1. Comparison of the number of Dryad datasets (for UT Austin-affiliated datasets and datasets across all affiliations) with a timestamp in a given year across three timestamps. *availableYear* and *publicationYear (DataCite)* are fields derived from the DataCite API (the former is extracted from a full timestamp; the latter is verbatim); *publicationYear (Dryad)* is derived from a full date field in the Dryad API. These dates should be congruent (similar to the *availableYear* and *publicationYear (Dryad)* fields), but there is a marked discrepancy in 2024 and 2025, with smaller discrepancies in 2019 and 2020. This dataset (Gee 2025b) omits file-level DOIs, which are retrieved from the DataCite API but not the Dryad API. Data as of July 1, 2025.

Examination of specific datasets in the DataCite API, the Dryad API, and DataCite Commons (web interface), as well as aggregate data for all Dryad datasets in both APIs, revealed that for most Dryad datasets published in 2024, the *publicationYear* field was, at some point, updated to list '2025.' At least for UT Austin-affiliated datasets, other DataCite fields such as *date.Issued* and *registered* displayed full timestamps with the correct year. This appears unrelated to the *updated* field, which almost always lists a date in the current year, likely as part of the Make Data Count process (which requires regular updates to incorporate new metric data), and also appears unrelated to versioning since most other datasets published prior to 2024 have congruent timestamps in other fields and on the landing page (i.e. if *publicationYear* was affected by versioning, there should be a more even distribution of discordant dates across many years). Additionally, when examining the full corpus of Dryad datasets, there remain several hundred with a *publicationYear* of 2024 (Fig. A1).

Across all Dryad datasets, nearly 13,000 had discordant publication year fields between the DataCite and Dryad APIs (Gee 2025b). There are two periods in which the annual count based on DataCite metadata is much higher than that based on Dryad metadata (2019–2020, 2025) and one period in which the inverse is true (2024), indicating that the discordance goes both ways (some datasets appear younger than they are, while others appear older than they are; Fig. A1). The *publicationYear* field is convenient for annual summaries since it does not require extracting the year from a full timestamp and is used by DataCite to create automatic summaries in its REST API and as a primary filter in DataCite Commons. In order to ensure accurate analysis, this workflow pivoted to use a different DataCite field from which year had to be extracted (*registered*), which is suboptimal because these fields should, in theory, be distinct

timestamps that may not be equivalent at finer timescales (e.g., month, day). This issue was brought to the attention of Dryad staff and resolved several months later in mid-July, but it potentially impacted other processes that involved retrieval of static Dryad records from DataCite in recent months.

Discordance in date metadata is not exclusive to Dryad; there appears to be a common issue in old Figshare datasets that have been versioned in which one creation date listed for the parent DOI is the most recent date of publication (*dates.date* where *dates.dateType='Created'*) and another (*created*) is the earliest date of publication (e.g., for Prokop 2013, with 65 versions between 2013 and 2023, both years appear in different creation date fields; dates for *updated* are also discordant), and likely similar patterns likely exist in other repositories but were not identified here. Some discordance over time is to be expected as repositories change their practices (although metadata discordance in general can sometimes be remedied by re-curation), whereas the issue with Dryad metadata was systemic but without a clear connection to a changed practice.

Mendeley Data

The third case study pertains to changes to affiliation recording and crosswalking in Mendeley Data. Based on examination of metadata for deposits affiliated with UT Austin, which is not, and has never been, an institutional member, Mendeley Data historically only crosswalked affiliation metadata to DataCite for institutional members. However, affiliation metadata was (sometimes) still recorded for authors at non-member institutions on dataset landing pages. Mendeley Data then appears to have started crosswalking all affiliation metadata to DataCite, regardless of institutional membership, in 2023; the timing suggests a connection to involvement in GREI. However, UT Austin-affiliated datasets published prior to 2023, of which there appear to be at

least several dozen to potentially several hundred based on a web interface search, still do not have affiliation metadata in DataCite, (e.g., Jayadev et al. 2020; House and Boehm 2021; Solomon-Lane et al. 2022). The data that can be obtained from the DataCite API will thus underestimate the total volume of affiliated Mendeley Data deposits and, if taken at face value, give a misleading impression that this repository was only used by affiliated researchers within the past few years. This case study is also an excellent demonstration of the importance of re-curation for improving quality of already-published datasets' metadata.

Figure A2. Comparison of annual volume of affiliated Mendeley Data datasets as retrieved from the DataCite API. Data as of November 21, 2025.

Figshare

The fourth case study pertains to affiliation metadata in Figshare and is multi-faceted, touching not only on metadata plasticity but also on re-curation, the value of data sharing, and a more common use case for data sharing (reproducibility). As part of the development of the secondary workflow to identify affiliated Figshare datasets that lack affiliation metadata, this study examined the dataset from the RADS study (Hofelich Mohr and Narlock 2024), specifically the CSV versions (rather than the RData versions) of the files. Initially, the focus was on identifying which journals and publishers were associated with affiliated Figshare deposits (Table 5; Gee 2025b), and because the CSV files flatten any nested fields from the JSON response into ‘NA’ entries, this examination re-queried these deposits’ DataCite records through the DataCite API. Incidentally, when examining the new output, a significant number of deposits were detected that lack affiliation metadata matching any one of the six RADS institutions (Table A1); many included no affiliation metadata at all.

Table A1. Summary of whether Figshare datasets previously reported with a RADS institution affiliation still include this linking metadata. Counts represent the retained records after removal of DOIs ending in ‘.v*’ (i.e. retaining only the ‘parent’ DOI). Matching was done using the institutional strings used in the RADS DataCite query. ‘Percent matched’ is essentially the percent of datasets that ‘should’ have been retrieved, assuming that all current DataCite affiliation metadata is accurate. *This count includes some duplication when a dataset was originally listed with multiple RADS institutions; it is counted for each institution.

Institution	Total count*	Unmatched count	Percent matched
Cornell	298	136	54.3%
Duke	91	58	36.2%

Michigan	185	123	33.5%
Minnesota	112	56	50.0%
Virginia Tech	141	129	8.51%
Washington U	268	224	16.4%
TOTAL	1,096	726	33.7%

Multiple hypotheses and their resultant predictions were developed to explain the widespread lack of RADS affiliation metadata among purportedly affiliated Figshare deposits.

1. *Hypothesis:* The metadata discrepancies are related to the methodology of Johnston et al. (2024), either to the process of searching for DOIs in DataCite or in processing a DataCite output.
 - a. *Prediction:* If a methodological flaw (e.g., capture of large numbers of ‘false positives’) is the cause, these discrepancies should also appear for other repositories at similar frequencies.
2. *Hypothesis:* The metadata discrepancies are related to Figshare, potentially related to the automation of dataset and metadata creation at scale through publisher partners.
 - a. *Prediction:* If a Figshare-specific process is the cause, these discrepancies should be primarily restricted to Figshare.

To this end, 4,000 dataset DOIs from the RADS dataset were randomly selected and queried for current affiliation metadata through the DataCite API. The code for this resampling uses a set seed [*random_state*] and thus can be independently reproduced (Gee 2025a), but the dataset is also included in the data publication (Gee 2025b). This workflow then looked for exact

matches for the search strings used by the RADS study. Of the 315 DOIs that were returned without a match to a RADS institution, more than 90% were Figshare deposits (Table A2; Gee 2025b). This provided compelling evidence for the second hypothesis: that the discrepancy in affiliation metadata is related to Figshare specifically rather than to some aspect of the dataset retrieval workflow.

Table A2. Comparison of unmatched and total counts of records for repositories with at least one unmatched dataset in a random re-sampling of 4,000 dataset DOIs from the RADS dataset (Hofelich Mohr and Narlock, 2024). Seventy-six repositories were captured in this random sampling process, but only those with at least one unmatched dataset ($n = 4$) are individually listed.

Repository	Total count	Unmatched count	Unmatched percent
Figshare	443	290	65.4%
Harvard Dataverse	1,832	6	0.327%
Neotoma	32	14	43.7%
Zenodo	563	5	0.884%
All other repositories	1,230	0	0.00%
TOTAL	4,000	315	7.87%

Examination of individual datasets for the four repositories with unmatched records provided further evidence that this is a systemic Figshare issue. For Harvard Dataverse, all but one of the unmatched datasets is listed with ‘Duke Kunshan University’ as an affiliation, indicating a pseudo-‘false positive’ match resulting from

non-exact search capability in *rdatacite* (Duke Kunshan is affiliated with Duke but is an independent institution, and there is no indication that Johnston et al. [2024] were seeking to include this institution in their results). The one remaining dataset (Teague 2019b) is interesting because it lists ‘University of Michigan’ (a RADS institution) in the metadata on the landing page, but the DataCite entry lists ‘MIT’ as the only affiliation. The author of that dataset is presently affiliated with MIT but was not affiliated at the time of their dataset publication, and the dataset has never been versioned. Additionally, the same author published another dataset on the same day, in the same dataverse, in Harvard Dataverse that lists the University of Michigan on both the landing page and in the DataCite entry (Teague 2019a).

For Zenodo, all unmatched datasets list of the following three (pseudo-)‘false positive’ affiliations: Duke Kunshan University, Duke Kinsman University (probably a typo of ‘Duke Kunshan University’), or West Virginia Institute of Technology.

For Neotoma, a specialist paleontological database, all 14 unmatched datasets list at least one of author who is properly affiliated with the institution the datasets were linked to in the RADS dataset (Minnesota), but for some reason, the affiliation metadata no longer exist in DataCite. It may be that metadata were accidentally erased in a platform overhaul or transition.

For Figshare, most datasets that still have affiliation metadata in their DataCite entry only list Chinese-based institutions. More than a third currently lack any affiliation metadata, and random spot-checking did not identify researchers with a previous affiliation with a RADS institution. The workflow did not identify any datasets with the same ‘false positives,’ although there are some institutions with many overlapping words (e.g., ‘University of Virginia’; ‘University of Electronic Science and Technology of China’; ‘Northwestern Polytechnical University’).

The RData files of the RADS dataset, which preserve the original structure from the API response retrieved in 2022 and thus the original affiliation metadata, were also examined. Inspection of random Figshare datasets identified ones in which at least one author had an extreme number of affiliations, as many as 68 in one example (Zhang et al., 2021, linked to Washington University in St. Louis), with affiliations sometimes spanning multiple continents and, crucially, including at least one RADS institution. cursory examination of these authors' online profiles (e.g., ORCIDs) and the related articles did not support either such extensive affiliation or any previous or current connection to a RADS institution. As a final test, random Figshare entries were inspected in the 2023 DataCite public data file (DataCite, 2024), which showed the same peculiar metadata patterns.

This exploration provides compelling evidence that the discovered metadata discrepancies are not the result of a methodological flaw in the RADS study but rather are the result of issues with how certain metadata in Figshare were created or managed (Hypothesis #2). The majority of purportedly affiliated Figshare deposits that currently show no affiliation to a RADS institution were last updated between February and March of 2024 (the final RADS dataset was collected in late 2022; Hofelich Mohr and Narlock, 2024). Because most of these deposits appear to have been mediated through publishers, the observation suggests large-scale automated creation of erroneous metadata, followed by large-scale re-curation, possibly related to an effort to automatically link affiliations based on an author's name (and thus that common names would be linked to many more affiliations than unique ones). However, I am not aware of any public acknowledgement of such an action, and Figshare did not respond to an email query requesting information

on this discovery. In some instances, the affiliation metadata appears to have been overwritten (re-curated) to the ‘correct’ metadata (congruent with that of the linked article; e.g., Zhang et al. 2021), but in many others, the affiliation metadata has been entirely erased (e.g., Li 2020, linked to the University of Minnesota; Zheng et al. 2022, linked to Duke). Presumably, it was not just datasets linked to RADS institutions’ that were impacted, and large-scale deletion of affiliation metadata without replacement (as a quick solution to erroneous entries) could explain, in part, why the number of affiliated Figshare deposits that are currently retrievable through the DataCite API is so low. Without express confirmation from Figshare, this remains merely an informed hypothesis, but it is difficult to conceive how hundreds of datasets that were definitively affiliated with just six institutions in 2022 are no longer affiliated.

This final case study in particular underscores several points. Firstly, it emphasizes the importance of data sharing and of depositing static versions of datasets specific to a study when working with dynamic resources like APIs where data and/or metadata can be deleted or altered in a way that does not preserve (or publicly expose) previous versions. Although provision of code and parameters may be sufficient to repeat a query, if the data source has been altered (e.g., change in affiliation metadata), it could still be impossible to reproduce the original results (such code and parameters are provided for the RADS study; Johnston et al. 2024; Hofelich Mohr and Narlock, 2024). This study did not set out to test the reproducibility of the RADS study but was able to do so in this instance thanks to the provision of the data necessary to test this hypothesis.

Secondly, this case study underscores the potential for complications arising from automation of some or all aspects of dataset publication. Automation facilitates efficient scaling but also requires rigorous and continual quality control to ensure that an automated process has not deviated from its intended function or introduced unexpected errors. Figshare’s process of

programmatically creating and publishing datasets is, to the best of my knowledge, unique among generalist repositories, and although it has certain benefits (e.g., synchronized time-release with the associated article, a coveted feature by researchers), this case study demonstrates that it can introduce quality issues at large scales, and there are other demonstrated areas in need of improvement in this process (e.g., automated keyword parsing/creation that includes HTML tags and other poorly constructed or generic terms; see Gee et al. 2023, for example).

Finally, this case study underscores the dynamic nature of metadata (e.g., Hendricks et al. 2020; Strecker 2025) and the value of open infrastructure that provides continuous, real-time access to those metadata (e.g., public REST APIs). Static public data files are sometimes recommended for large-scale retrieval, with recommendations from both Crossref and DataCite to keep these up to date by using a REST API to retrieve records added after the release of the static file. However, as this case study demonstrates, corpuses of metadata can be altered not only by the addition of novel records but also by modification of previously sampled records.

Appendix B. Workflow validation

Various validation processes were carried out during the development of this workflow. Some of these have already been discussed in the main-text and resulted in scripted processes that are still evident in the codebase (Gee 2025a). The best example of this is the cross-validation process described in the main text with select repositories (Dryad, TDR, Zenodo), which was initially automated and then complemented by granular manual examination of specific datasets or search results in the web platforms of these repositories. The process was initially used to identify other permutations of ‘UT Austin’ to be added to the general DataCite query. For example, initial queries through the DataCite API returned very few TDR datasets, which was one of the impetuses for expanding queried permutations of UT Austin. I then manually examined the individual DataCite API entries of published TDR datasets that were known to exist but that were not returned from the broad DataCite queries and discovered the malformed affiliation metadata for many TDR datasets. In general, the development of this workflow benefited from directly managing an institutional data repository for which I have a more in-depth understanding of data publishing and metadata crosswalking processes. This cross-validation process with select repositories’ APIs is retained in the workflow because of granular affiliation metadata for some deposits (e.g., affiliation includes departmental information or postal information), as these affiliations are too numerous and scarce to warrant adding to the list of permutations of the institutional name (due to a cap on how many strings can be queried in one DataCite API call).

Other validation steps are retained in secondary scripts that are not always intended for downstream re-use (Gee 2025a); an example is the Dryad case study mentioned in Appendix A where temporary discordance between certain date fields in the DataCite and Dryad APIs led to

drastically different summaries of annual publication volume (Fig. A1; Gee 2025b). The code for validation processes such as this (or the reanalysis of the RADS dataset with specific emphasis on purportedly affiliated Figshare deposits; Gee 2025a) is provided mainly for reproducing the specific results of this study. Another example is the provision of the script to calculate what subset of affiliated datasets can be recovered with either a ROR-based search in a single metadata field or a single-string-based search in a single metadata field (Gee 2025a); this process was known to be incomplete in retrieval from the beginning but was used to establish a baseline for increasing retrieval coverage. These processes often involved examination and comparison of specific datasets' metadata in different platforms (e.g., comparison of publication date in the Dryad web interface, the Dryad API, the DataCite web interface [DataCite Commons], and the DataCite API); in most instances, these were randomly selected from datasets that were retrieved through the primary workflow, although in some instances, personal knowledge of a specific dataset (not necessarily affiliated with UT Austin) in a certain platform led to examination of other datasets. Having published several datasets in repositories myself, I was also able to examine how metadata that I had (or had not) provided with my deposits was reflected in the DataCite API. Similarly, for processes involving retrieval of article metadata through Crossref or OpenAlex, singular articles were targeted for examination of different metadata fields, some of which are my own publications.

Finally, much of the exploration of Figshare metadata was drawn from the author's personal experience as an active scientific researcher with several dozen peer-reviewed publications. For example, the integration between Figshare and some scholarly publishers like Springer Nature, Taylor & Francis, and PLOS in which files uploaded as 'supplemental information' are automatically published on Figshare upon publication of the associated article is

not well-known among researchers and even to editors, as no Figshare account is necessary for the depositor. My knowledge that this process exists and at least some aspects of how it functions (e.g., sometimes assigning each file a separate DOI) is based on first-hand experience as a researcher – I personally “published” eight Figshare deposits, mostly through Taylor & Francis titles (e.g., Gee et al. 2021, 2023), before discovering that this is how supplemental information is hosted by the publisher. In these titles in which I have published, there is no indication that this integration exists in the journal instructions, submission portal, or any part of the production process. I have never logged into Figshare, and none of my auto-created deposits record even basic author metadata such as my ORCID or affiliation at the time, so it seems unlikely that I would be able to claim, edit, or version any of these datasets to improve their quality (although I have noticed at least one instance in which either the journal or Figshare versioned the dataset without my knowledge let alone any request from me; compare Gee et al. 2019 and Gee et al. 2020).

Appendix C. Additional details on the cross-validation process

As noted in the main text, the primary purpose of the cross-validation process is identification of additional permutations of a focal institution's name that can be added to a multi-permutation query (excluding highly granular ones that are likely one-offs). This process thus mainly focuses on datasets that were discovered through a specific repository API but not from the DataCite API in order to improve the affiliation-based DataCite query (e.g., adding a new permutation of 'UT Austin'). However, the inverse (datasets only found in DataCite's API but not in a repository's API) also occurs, albeit very rarely. The explanations for these edge cases are likely repository-specific and are often unclear, but they are noted here with possible explanations.

The first example results from a lack of updated or crosswalked metadata for old deposits. For example, some dated deposits in Dryad (e.g., McTavish et al. 2015) and Zenodo (e.g., Dixon 2014) have affiliation metadata recorded on the landing page and in the repository API, but, as of this work, this metadata has not been crosswalked to DataCite. This is not unlike historic (pre-2023) datasets in Mendeley Data that lack a researcher from a member institution and for which no affiliation metadata is recorded.

The second example is when a DOI appears to have been published but was then taken down, without any public-facing metadata label or explanation; rather than redirecting to the "DOI not found" page on doi.org (which typically indicates a lack of DOI activation), these DOIs redirect to a repository page indicating that the dataset was not found. This was observed for Dryad (e.g., Nandakumar et al. 2020a; Larter and Ryan 2023) and TDR (Hodges 2019a). For Dryad, it is presumed that these datasets were de-accessioned; this repository does not currently have a tombstone process. Curiously, there appears to be a dataset with nearly identical metadata and a public DOI (Nandakumar et

al. 2020b) for one of the non-functional Dryad DOIs (Nandakumar et al. 2020a). For TDR, the explanation is less clear (Dataverse installations have a tombstone process), but the unavailable dataset also appears to have a duplicate, publicly available dataset with nearly identical metadata in TDR (Hodges 2019b).

The final example is a TDR dataset that is published and publicly accessible, but the DOI has not been activated (Bernard 2017). All instances of non-functional DOIs have been reported to their respective repositories and demonstrate the added utility of this workflow for identifying datasets in need of metadata re-curation.

Appendix D. Tested approaches to programmatic retrieval of mediated Figshare deposits with Crossref DOIs: the PLOS case study

As noted in the main text, the sheer volume of mediated Figshare deposits with Crossref DOIs (millions) render a process like that developed for mediated Figshare deposits with DataCite DOIs impractical because of the time and API conditions (e.g., rate limiting allowances, server stability) that would be necessary just to retrieve all such objects (it could be more tractable with the public data file). Three different programmatic approaches were tested with PLOS specifically (not the only partner to mediate Figshare deposits with Crossref DOIs), but they are either very time-intensive, or they are not readily transferable to other publisher partners. The code for all three is provided as a proof of concept (Gee 2025a).

The first approach involves identifying a list of affiliated articles published by a partner (PLOS), constructing a hypothetical SI file based on observed DOI construction patterns for that publisher (adding a ‘.s00*’ or ‘.t00*’ suffix to the article DOI), and pinging the URL to see if it exists. This process is rather time-consuming because it requires individual queries to test the existence of each hypothetical DOI, and even if a DOI does exist, no additional information is returned. The testing could be done with the Crossref API in order to obtain some metadata, but this is not recommended given the volume of API calls that would be necessary. All of the files associated with one article would have to be retrieved for collective assessment (e.g., SI files 1–19 could be accessory non-data files and file S20 could be a raw data file), and a means of assessing the content (‘nature’) of files from the very limited Crossref metadata remains elusive. The approach in particular is discouraged for use because of its time cost and is provided in the codebase only to demonstrate that this was explored.

The second approach is to use text-scraping (through the *beautifulsoup4* module; Richardson 2025) to target the HTML blocks that contain information about SI files. For PLOS articles, this provides more information than the Crossref API because the HTML blocks contain additional, valuable information like the title of the deposit, which includes a value from a semi-controlled vocabulary (e.g., Figure, Table, Text); a description of the file; and the file format (e.g., DOCX, XLSX, PDF). Additional fields could either be scraped from the page or retrieved from the Crossref records for the article (e.g., author information) and collectively could be used, for example, to assess whether a given file or at least one file from a multi-file set for one article qualifies as ‘data.’ This process is more time-efficient than the first approach, but it is intrinsically sensitive to any future modifications to the HTML code and would require a custom approach for each publisher partner’s distinct HTML formatting. Whether other publisher partners who use Crossref for mediated Figshare deposits provide the same level of metadata for SI content in the web version of articles was not assessed. In early stages of testing, there was also some variation in how metadata were entered between PLOS titles.

The third approach is extremely quick but very coarse-grained and involves the use of the PLOS Open Science Indicators (OSI) dataset (Public Library of Science 2024). This dataset, which is on version 10 (the workflow was tested on version 9) and under continuous development, was created through analysis of the entire corpus of PLOS articles and includes a categorization of where data were shared. The secondary workflow using this dataset retrieves a list of affiliated PLOS articles and then filters the PLOS OSI dataset for any affiliated article that has data shared in part or in whole through SI, which is in actuality the mediated Figshare process. This method assumes that the PLOS algorithms for identifying ‘data’ are philosophically aligned with those of the investigator and provides no additional information on the count, nature (e.g., file formats),

or DOIs of these mediated deposits. It also relies on periodic versioning of the core dataset to be useful in the long-term and will quickly become slightly outdated after release. This approach mainly proved useful in early testing and exploration because it runs extremely quickly (< 60 seconds), and it could be sufficient for certain use cases (e.g., a quick approximation).

Appendix E. Additional cleaning processes

As mentioned in the main text, there are likely to be additional cleaning steps for smaller-scale repositories, but these will likely be specific to each institution since they mostly involve specialist repositories with more heterogenous usage (or lack thereof) across disciplines and research institutions. Some examples for UT Austin are noted here, mainly to contextualize specific lines of code for these granular processes (Gee 2025a), some of which target individual datasets after manual examination of the outputs during workflow development.

For the Environmental Molecular Science Laboratory (EMSL), it appears that individual but related samples are deposited with separate DOIs, as there are sets of datasets with identical metadata (authors, publication date, etc.), separate (but numerically sequential) DOIs, and the same type of data in each deposit (e.g., 15 deposits titled ‘Data for EMSL Project 47414 from March 2020’; Gao et al. 2020a, 2020b, 2020c, are cited here as examples). These were deduplicated based on a combination of metadata fields (dataset title, first author, *relationType*, *relatedIdentifier*, *containerIdentifier*).

For DesignSafe, affiliation metadata is sub-optimally entered in the *contributor.name* field, rather than in an affiliation field, so it is not apparent which affiliation corresponds to which author(s). Additionally, because the repository is hosted at the Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC) at UT Austin, all datasets list ‘University of Texas at Austin’ as a ‘contributor’ regardless of whether a UT Austin researcher was actually involved. Examination of random deposits suggested that when a UT Austin researcher was legitimately involved, the affiliation will specifically be ‘University of Texas at Austin (utexas.edu).’ This distinction was used to remove DesignSafe entries without this particular form of the affiliation.

Finally, listed repository names were corrected and standardized. For example, some Zenodo datasets do not list Zenodo as the *publisher*; as this is a freeform editable field in Zenodo (in contrast to many other repositories in which the repository is locked as the value in this field), any value can be entered in this field (e.g., Aziz Zanjani [2024] lists ‘The Seismic Record’ as the *publisher*). There are probably appropriate scenarios for entering a value other than the hosting repository, but for the purposes of this work, any deposit with ‘zenodo’ in the DOI string was changed to list Zenodo as the publisher.

Reusers of this workflow will need to manually check their own outputs, as additional outliers will likely be unique to an institution (the ability for authors to edit the publisher field exists in other platforms; the Global Biodiversity Information Facility [GBIF] and Finnish FairData are other examples encountered here). Longer-tenured repositories are more likely to also have different permutations of their name listed in metadata records (e.g., ‘Texas Data Repository’ vs. ‘Texas Research Data Repository’), which were standardized here for identified repositories.

The workflow also contains an optional additional processing of Dataverse deposits (these could be Harvard Dataverse for any institution or an institutional data repository on Dataverse software like TDR). I have observed that some authors create multiple ‘datasets’ in TDR, each labeled as ‘dataset’ in the Dataverse parlance (a DOI-backed container labeled as ‘dataset’ in DataCite), that all pertain to a single manuscript/article and that are nested under a single ‘dataverse’ (a non-DOI-backed container). Examples include five datasets (code, reconstruction parameters, system parameters, results, measurements) for one study on zebrafish (Yang 2024a, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e); and four datasets (two types of data, experimental conditions,

README) for one study on mechano-lysis in blood clots (Rausch 2025a, 2025b, 2025c, 2025d). Authors seem to separate materials based on format or an internal organizational delimiter (e.g., samples, specimens), rather than along metadata (e.g., different authorship lists, different licensing), and in contrast to the mediated Figshare process, they are not splitting each file into its own deposit (a standalone deposit for a README file may be an exception). Nonetheless, this practice can be considered to partially inflate the number of Dataverse ‘datasets’ because one could argue that all of the files would be in a single DOI-backed dataset in another repository that lacks an overarching container. The division of materials is probably the result of researchers taking advantage of the ‘dataverse’ container, which has no equivalent in most other repositories. This optional processing step consolidates objects with the same publication date, creators, and rights into a single entry. Although it is possible to retrieve dataverse metadata through the Dataverse API, some researchers create more expansive dataverses, beyond the level of one manuscript, that house multiple sets of deposits, and this step requires an additional API call. The resultant counts from this process can be drastically lower than the pre-consolidation count: if applied to the UT Austin datasets, the original 1,487 DOIs are consolidated into 949 (63%) entries. Because the observed splitting of materials in these instances is both logical and manual, and I have occasionally observed similar intentional splitting in other repositories, the results described in the main text do not incorporate this step.

Finally, while developing rules for cleaning and consolidating deposits, duplicate publishing of the same dataset in different repositories was identified. Presently, three pairs affiliated with UT Austin are identified: TDR + Zenodo (Samineni 2022; Samineni and Kumar 2022); Dryad + ScienceDB (Wang et al. 2023, 2023b); and Harvard Dataverse + Zenodo (Ishikawa et al. 2025a, 2025b). The reasons for this duplication are unclear, but with their

identification, the researchers could be contacted to inquire about this practice. This duplication is different than paired Dryad-Zenodo deposits that share the same title and most other metadata fields and that will be retrieved if a workflow user includes resource types other than ‘dataset’ in the query. These related deposits result from a partnership in which a researcher submitting to Dryad has the option to create a linked Zenodo deposit for supplemental information and/or software (Lowenberg 2021). Linked Zenodo deposits will contain separate files, have different resource type labels, and be licensed differently, but other metadata attributes like title and authorship are shared with the Dryad deposit.

Appendix F. Additional metadata assessments

As mentioned in the main text, assessing metadata of affiliated datasets is a core objective at UT Austin. This appendix presents several additional assessments that are already in the existing codebase.

Licensing

Licensing is a common challenge for researchers and is intertwined with the propensity of researchers to publish mixed-format deposits (e.g., tabular data and Python code) since the ideal licensing for data and software often differs. This is evidenced through a small number of ‘dataset’ objects with software licensing, such as Apache, BSD, and MIT (Fig. A3; Gee 2025b). Initial examination of the distribution of licenses among datasets appears to indicate that the CC0 license waiver / public domain designation is by far the most common, a positive sign since this is often considered the most appropriate treatment for data *sensu stricto* in the United States. However, some repositories only use CC0 licensing (e.g., Dryad) or have CC0 set to the default and require researchers to manually select or enter non-CC0 terms if they so desire (e.g., Dataverse installations). This raises questions over whether authors of datasets with CC0 licensing made an intentional, informed decision to use this treatment based on their understanding of intellectual property or, more likely, in my opinion, they were required to and did not understand the implications or did not care enough to object; were not aware of their ability to change the license; or simply did not pay any attention to the licensing. The joint number of CC0 datasets between TDR and Dryad is around 1,700; if just these two repositories are omitted, the number of CC0 drops significantly to be in line with that of CC BY-licensed deposits (Fig. A3).

Figure A3. Comparison of licensing treatment for objects labeled as ‘datasets.’ Data are based on the *rightsIdentifier* field values and were standardized for inconsistent entry of a given license. The data represent all datasets retrieved in the general affiliation-based DataCite query and the cross-validation with specific repositories’ APIs; mediated Figshare deposits with DataCite DOIs, which usually have CC BY licensing, are not included ($n = 3,138$). The three most common treatments are shown in the top subplot, while the remaining, less common

treatments are shown in the bottom subplot with a differently scaled x-axis to make comparisons of low-volume treatments easier to discern. Data as of November 21, 2025.

Deposit size

The average size of affiliated deposits and the frequency of “large” datasets (semi-arbitrarily defined as 50 GB or larger) is growing as computational abilities increase, with terabyte-size datasets becoming increasingly common. This poses numerous challenges for repositories with respect to infrastructure for handling large uploads and downloads, the costs associated with long-term retention, and ensuring that they are well-documented (e.g., many large datasets include compressed archives, the contents of which are not immediately clear but which can be described in a README file). For data repositories with smaller budgets (compare an institutional data repository to Zenodo, which is supported by CERN, for example), these questions are especially pressing. Assessing trends in published dataset size (Fig. A4) and where particularly large datasets are deposited (mainly Dryad and TDR for UT Austin) can facilitate long-term planning for a given repository, and for university research data staff who receive questions about disposition of large data, provide a quick high-level overview of potential options for other researchers (finding repository file and deposit size limits often requires individually checking repository websites; this information is not included in indexes like re3data, for example).

Figure A4. Histogram of the number of datasets within different size bins. The range of deposit sizes for affiliated datasets goes from approximately zero to 720.5 GB, with a mean of 2.5 GB and a median of 2.4 MB (for datasets with deposit size information). ‘No data’ means that there is no information on the deposit size and is different from ‘Empty,’ which is a legitimate 0 kB deposit. The data represent all datasets retrieved in the general affiliation-based DataCite query and the cross-validation with specific repositories’ APIs; mediated Figshare deposits with DataCite DOIs are not included ($n = 3,138$). Data as of November 21, 2025.

Dataset title quality

A common observation when examining research datasets in non-curated repositories is low-quality general metadata, such as generic titles like “Raw data” or generic keywords like “outputs.” Improving these metadata is a relatively low-effort action that can significantly

increase findability of datasets, especially if there are little to no additional descriptive text fields (e.g., an abstract or description field). Identifying existing datasets with such metadata can be useful in a variety of ways, such as engaging with researchers to suggest low-effort metadata updates like adding more keywords or creating a more informative title; proposing suggestions for future deposits (e.g., if versioning is not possible for a dataset); and identifying areas where many researchers would benefit from broader educational outreach (e.g., workshops, LibGuides). Dataset titles are used as one example of a general metadata assessment here.

The length of a dataset title is not directly correlated with its quality. Short titles can be informative if they contain unique, discipline- or format-specific terms, and long titles can be relatively uninformative with respect to the dataset itself (e.g., reusing a lengthy manuscript title). An assessment tool in this workflow defines lists of typically uninformative words such as grammatical articles and common research terms like ‘data’; it is acknowledged that there are exceptions to most rules, but these are fairly reliable general rules. The script then counts the total number of descriptive words (i.e. all words not in a prescribed list; Fig. A5).

Figure A5. Histogram of the number of descriptive words in the title of affiliated datasets.

The range goes from zero to 41, with a mean of 8.7 and a median of 8. The data represent all datasets retrieved in the general affiliation-based DataCite query and the cross-validation with specific repositories’ APIs; additionally, consolidated Figshare deposits are excluded since their ‘title’ fields contain multiple deposit titles ($n = 3,126$). Data as of November 21, 2025.

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